

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD)

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable 3.3

Recalibration of the photon sensitivity of the
SOHO/EPHIN and BepiColombo/SIXS

EU's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme

Grant Agreement 101135044

UNIVERSITY
OF TURKU

Kiel University
Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel

UNIVERSITY
OF OULU

Lead Beneficiary	<i>Christian-Albrechts-University</i>
Author	M. Köberle , J. Gieseler, B. Heber, M. Hörlöck, S. Jensen, P. Kühl, P. Oleynik, A. Papaioannou, I. Sandberg & R. Vainio

Work Package	WP3: Cross- and re-calibration
Task	Task 3.3
Deliverable	D3.3: Recalibration of the photon sensitivity of the SOHO/EPHIN and BepiColombo/SIXS
Date for Deliverable	27 June 2025

Change Log				
Version	Date	Author(s)	Reason for Modification	Status
1	2025-06-27	Köberle et al.	New Document	Submitted
2				

Dissemination Level	
Public	X
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Contents

Contents	3
List of Figures	4
List of Tables	5
List of Acronyms	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
Recalibration of the photon sensitivity of the SOHO/EPHIN and BepiColombo/SIXS	8
1 Introduction	8
2 Instrumentation	9
2.1 The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN)	9
2.1.1 GEometry ANd Tracking (GEANT) simulations of EPHIN aboard Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) for photons	11
2.1.2 Expected Count Rate for the X1.6 and X4.8 Flares on October 22, 2014 and July 23, 2002	11
2.1.3 Effect of Lower Detection Thresholds in Solid State Detector (SSD) A	13
2.2 The Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer (SIXS)	16
3 Conclusions	19
Bibliography	20

List of Figures

1	Sketch (left) and realization in the GEANT model (right) of the EPHIN instrument, adapted from Kühl et al. (2020) and Köberle et al. (2024).	9
2	The upper and lower panel display the single detector count and the background corrected rates during the July 9, 1996 Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) event, respectively (for details see text and Sierks et al. 1997, and references therein).	10
3	From left to right are shown the energy dependent response function for SSD A with an energy threshold of 3, 15 and 30 keV, respectively. For details see Köberle et al. (2025).	11
4	Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager (RHESSI) detector count rates and photon spectra for the X1.6 flare on October 22, 2014 (see Thalmann et al. 2015, and references therein)	12
5	Photon spectrum for the X4.6 class flare on July 7, 2002 (see for example Suarez-Garcia et al. 2006; Lin 2011, and references therein).	12
6	The upper and lower panel display the single detector count rates of EPHIN's SSD during the solar flare on October 21, 2014 and July 7, 2002, respectively. The horizontal lines mark the time for which the X-ray spectra from RHESSI were measured (for details see text).	13
7	The left and right panel show the simulated count rate vs. threshold for the October 22, 2014 and July 7, 2002 solar X-ray flare.	14
8	The left and right panels display a 12 minute time interval during the onset of the solar X-ray flare on October 22, 2014 showing the uncorrected and corrected count rate in all segments of SSD A, respectively. For details see text.	14
9	Roll angle during July 1996 and October 2014. While the observation was nominal in 1996 SOHO was tilted by 180° in 2014. For details see text.	15
10	The SIXS-P detector head (from Huovelin et al. 2020, Fig. 8).	16
11	RHESSI photon spectra obtained for 8 different periods (data provided by A. Warmuth - an External Advisory Committee (EAC) member of SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD)).	17
12	Effective area for photon detection of SIXS-P for a parallel beam normal to the Side 0 detector, broken down to responses of the individual electron energy channels.	18

List of Tables

1	Computed counting rates of SIXS due to eight solar X-ray flares as observed by RHESSI (cf. Fig 11).	18
---	---	----

List of Acronyms

BepiC	BepiColombo
COSTEP	Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer
EAC	External Advisory Committee
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
RHESSI	Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SSD	Solid State Detector

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report explores the potential insights gained from single-count measurements of solar X-ray events on [SOHO EPHIN](#) and [SIXS-P](#) aboard BepiColombo.

Specifically, the single detector counters [SSD-A](#) of [EPHIN](#) onboard [SOHO](#) are used to compare the expected count rates utilizing [RHESSI](#) measurements and the response function derived in [Köberle et al. \(2025\)](#).

A good agreement between the single detector counts in [SSD A](#) is found if the threshold of the detector is lowered to about 15 keV.

The photon sensitivity of the particle detector of BepiColombo/[SIXS](#) ([SIXS-P](#)) was also simulated. The instrument effective area for zero zenith angle on Side0, derived in [Köberle et al. \(2025\)](#), was used to evaluate the count rates expected for solar flares measured by [RHESSI](#). The result cannot yet be compared with observations, however, due to [SIXS](#) not being exposed to Sun in the cruise configuration of the mission.

1 Introduction

Several space-based instruments designed to observe solar X-rays utilize silicon solid-state detectors, owing to their excellent energy resolution, low noise, and compact design. Notable examples include:

- **RHESSI (Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager):** Utilized segmented germanium and silicon detectors for imaging and spectroscopy of solar flares in hard X-rays and gamma-rays [Lin et al. \(2002\)](#).
- **GOES XRS and EUVS (GOES-R series):** Although the primary X-ray sensor (XRS) uses ionization chambers, newer GOES instruments also incorporate silicon photodiode-based detectors in some EUV and X-ray channels [Detrick & Hill \(2007\)](#).
- **Hinode/XRT (X-Ray Telescope):** Uses a CCD made of silicon to capture images of the solar corona in soft X-rays [Golub et al. \(2007\)](#). The CCD effectively acts as a silicon detector sensitive to photon energies in the soft X-ray regime.
- **Solar Orbiter/STIX (Spectrometer/Telescope for Imaging X-rays):** Employs 32 Cadmium-Telluride (CdTe) detectors, but earlier concepts and associated instruments used silicon detectors for calibration and development [Krucker et al. \(2020\)](#).
- **MinXSS (Miniature X-ray Solar Spectrometer):** CubeSat-based mission using silicon drift detectors (SDDs) to measure solar soft X-ray spectra from 0.5 to 30 keV with high spectral resolution [Mason et al. \(2016\)](#).

2 Instrumentation

2.1 The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN)

The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN, Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) is part of the Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer (COSTEP) suite onboard SOHO. A schematic view of the

Figure 1: Sketch (left) and realization in the GEANT model (right) of the EPHIN instrument, adapted from Kühn et al. (2020) and Köberle et al. (2024).

EPHIN instrument together with its realization in the GEometry ANd Tracking (GEANT) model is shown in Fig. 1. The instrument consists of a stack of six SSDs (labeled A-F in Fig. 1) that is surrounded by a scintillation detector (G), which acts as an anticoincidence. Stopping ions are identified by applying the $\frac{dE}{dx} - E$ -method. Since the data rate is limited, energy losses in detectors A-E can only be transmitted for a statistical ensemble of all particles counted by EPHIN. A crude separation between electrons, protons, and helium has been introduced for different penetration depths, that is, different coincidences, by introducing different energy-loss thresholds in SSD A (for details see Müller-Mellin et al. 1995). To monitor time-dependent instrumental issues, various parameters are recorded independently of any coincidence condition, including the sensor and electronic box temperatures, leakage currents, and count rates of the six SSDs (A to F) and the anticoincidence scintillator (G) of EPHIN.

Among others EPHIN provides single detector count rates for all detectors ($A0_i$, $B0_i$, to G) for each segment i of SSD A and B. Fig. 2 displays the count rates of the 6 segments of SSD A during the July 9, 1996 SEP event (see also Sierks et al. 1997, and references therein). The time profile shows two increases in all segments of SSD A. The first is short and can be attributed to an X-ray solar flare discussed e.g. in Motorina et al. (2020). The second increase belongs to the energetic particle event.

From the time profiles shown in the figure, a distinct difference between the increase attributed to the X-ray flare and the SEP event becomes obvious. While all segment counts increase with the same amplitude this is not the case for the X-ray event. This is expected from the GEANT simulation as detailed in the next section.

Figure 2: The upper and lower panel display the single detector count and the background corrected rates during the July 9, 1996 SEP event, respectively (for details see text and [Sierks et al. 1997](#), and references therein).

2.1.1 GEANT simulations of EPHIN aboard SOHO for photons

The simulation of the EPHIN response to X-rays and γ -rays was performed using the GEANT4 Monte Carlo toolkit (Agostinelli et al. 2003). A pre-configured geometry of the instrument was used (see Fig. 1 and Köberle et al. 2024, and references therein).

A rectangular photon source (300 cm²) emitted photons at a 45° angle relative to the detector's axis, mimicking the direction of the Parker spiral. The photon spectrum followed a power law ($I \propto E^{-1}$), resulting in a uniform distribution in logarithmic energy bins (for details see Köberle et al. 2025).

Detector A is sensitive from about 1 keV (not shown here), with a dip around 5 keV due to titanium absorption NIST (2025). It peaks near 9 keV, then declines as the photoelectric cross-section drops.

At energies > 60 keV, Compton scattering dominates, and above 1 MeV, pair production contributes, though much of the resulting particle energy escapes the detector.

Figure 3: From left to right are shown the energy dependent response function for SSD A with an energy threshold of 3, 15 and 30 keV, respectively. For details see Köberle et al. (2025).

In what follows we evaluate the results of the GEANT4 simulation of the EPHIN instrument by comparing them with actual measurements during selected solar X-ray flare events. The focus is on expected count rates for specific events, the influence of the energy threshold, and the behavior of individual detector segments.

2.1.2 Expected Count Rate for the X1.6 and X4.8 Flares on October 22, 2014 and July 23, 2002

The simulation results are compared to data from the solar flares (X1.6 and X4.8-class) on October 22, 2014, and July 23, 2002. Figure 4 shows the RHESSI detector responses and the photon spectrum at four time points during the X1.6 flare. The corresponding maximum spectrum for the July 12, 2002 solar flare is shown in Fig. 5. The corresponding EPHIN A-detector count rates are shown in the upper and lower panels of Fig. 6.

The time of the flare spectrum at 14:05:58 UT is marked in the upper panel of Fig. 6 by the red dashed line. When the count rate in segment 0 exceeds a certain threshold, the outer ring segments are logically switched off (for details see Köberle et al. 2025). The spectrum at the given time is approximated using a power law ($a \approx -4.6$) and folded with the simulation response using the nominal threshold of 30 keV. The computed increase for the sum of all segments in SSD A (not shown in the upper panel) is about 5900 counts/min and can be compared to the measured one of about 390,000 counts/minute. An unexpected difference of a factor of 75 is obtained.

To validate the difference between the expected and measured count rates, we investigated the X4.8 X-ray flare occurring on July 7, 2002, that is discussed in Lin (2011). In our analysis, we used the RHESSI spectrum shown in Fig 5. The count rate time profile is shown in the lower panel of Fig. 6. The time of the flare spectrum is indicated by the vertical dashed line. Again, we find that the simulation underestimates the measured EPHIN count rate in segment 0 of SSD A by a factor of about 200. This discrepancy suggests that the simulation is not capable of taking into account all effects needed to ascribe to the

Figure 4: RHESSI detector count rates and photon spectra for the X1.6 flare on October 22, 2014 (see [Thalmann et al. 2015](#), and references therein)

Figure 5: Photon spectrum for the X4.6 class flare on July 7, 2002 (see for example [Suarez-Garcia et al. 2006](#); [Lin 2011](#), and references therein).

Figure 6: The upper and lower panel display the single detector count rates of EPHIN’s SSD during the solar flare on October 21, 2014 and July 7, 2002, respectively. The horizontal lines mark the time for which the X-ray spectra from RHESSI were measured (for details see text).

observations. One reason is the poor time resolution that does not allow us to determine the count rate at the time of the measured spectrum.

Another unexpected feature is the different count rates of two outer segments compared to the other ones. This effect should only become important if the effective threshold in SSD A is much lower than the nominal one of 30 keV. This becomes obvious when comparing the right panel with the other two panels of Fig. 3. Therefore, we investigate in what follows the impact of varying the detection threshold in SSD A.

2.1.3 Effect of Lower Detection Thresholds in SSD A

Fig. 7 shows in the left and right panels the expected count rates in minutes when lowering the energy loss threshold in SSD A for the October 22, 2014, and July 7, 2002, solar X-ray flare, respectively. For this purpose, the response functions are computed utilizing these different thresholds as described in more detail in Köberle et al. (2025). The dashed curves in the two panels are the result of an interpolation of the computed count rates at a given threshold. The line marked by setpoint gives the observed count rate during the flare time. An efficient threshold can be determined for which threshold energies the setpoint line is crossed. Lowering the assumed threshold from 30 keV to about 15.5 keV significantly improves the agreement between simulated and measured rates. Potential explanations include electronic noise,

temporal resolution ($2.5 \mu\text{s}$), and photon pile-up. The latter would indicate that the electronic threshold is higher than the effective threshold.

Figure 7: The left and right panel show the simulated count rate vs. threshold for the October 22, 2014 and July 7, 2002 solar X-ray flare.

Count rates in the single segments: Fig. 8 shows in its left and right panels the time profile of the uncorrected and corrected count rates of all segments during the onset of the October 22, 2014 X-ray event. While the segment count rate is expected to be the same as it was obtained in 1996 (see upper panel of Fig. 2) the values for segments 0 and 3 are significantly larger than for the others, indicating a different degradation of all segments of SSD A. After the onset, we find, as expected, two classes, with segment 1 and 2 showing lower values than the other ones. Note the discrepancy to the simulation that predicts segments 1 and 5 to have lower count rates. This is most likely due to the wrong numbering

Figure 8: The left and right panels display a 12 minute time interval during the onset of the solar X-ray flare on October 22, 2014 showing the uncorrected and corrected count rate in all segments of SSD A, respectively. For details see text.

of the segments, since the observations show no dependence on the roll angle (see for details D2.3 Köberle et al. 2025) as shown by comparing Fig 2 with Fig. 8. The roll during these periods is shown in the left and right panels of Fig. 9, respectively.

Figure 9: Roll angle during July 1996 and October 2014. While the observation was nominal in 1996 SOHO was tilted by 180° in 2014. For details see text.

It was shown that the segment count rate of **SSD A** can be used to investigate solar X-ray events. The response function has been computed by **Köberle et al. (2025)** and predicted that two of the six segments will have a lower count rate if an efficient energy threshold would be lower than 30 keV as found in the observations. Our detailed analysis of two events for which the photon spectrum was known resulted to a an efficient threshold of about 15 keV.

2.2 The Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer (SIXS)

Like for EPHIN, we also evaluated the photon response of the particle detector of SIXS (SIXS-P Huovelin et al. 2020) aboard BepiColombo (BepiC). SIXS-P consists of five planar silicon detectors with a thickness of $150\ \mu\text{m}$ around a $5\times 5\times 6.3\ \text{mm}^3$ CsI(Tl) parallelepiped scintillation crystal with a photodiode readout. All silicon detectors have a central round active area (diameter 2.5 mm) in the centre and a square anticoincidence area surrounding the central spot. The silicon detectors and the scintillator are housed in an aluminium collimator dome (with collimator rings that have their lower halves made of tungsten), as shown in Fig. 10. SIXS-P implements the ΔE -E method of particle identification, but at the lowest energies, the instrument relies on single detector measurements, i.e., measuring the pulse height in one of the silicon detectors with all other detector elements in anticoincidence. Thus, the lowest energy electron channels, in particular, are also sensitive to X-ray photons. The effective area of the instrument as a function of photon energy is evaluated in Köberle et al. (2025).

Figure 10: The SIXS-P detector head (from Huovelin et al. 2020, Fig. 8).

In this document, we present the response of SIXS-P to eight solar X-ray flare spectra measured by RHESSI (see Fig. 11). The counting rates due to photons in SIXS-P electron channels are computed by integrating the product of the X-ray flux spectrum (in units of photons/cm² s keV) and the effective area (in cm²) of the detector over the incident photon energy. We keep the threshold energy of the silicon detectors at their nominal value of 35 keV. The integration is extended from the threshold up to 300 keV, where the photon flux is deemed negligible given the small physical size of the detector. Since the instrument is not able to observe the Sun during the cruise phase of the mission, we cannot compare the measurements with observational data before the mission arrives at Mercury. Therefore, we have made the computations for a vertically incident photon beam, only, to obtain the maximum photon response of the instrument to the photon beam. The response functions of the electron channels E1–E4 are depicted in Fig. 12.

The computed counting rates of channels E1–E4 are given in Table 1. They range from a few counts per minute down to zero, depending on the flare and the energy channel. However, the values are computed for spectra measured at 1 AU, which means that at Mercury, the same flares would cause 4.5–

Figure 11: RHESSI photon spectra obtained for 8 different periods (data provided by A. Warmuth - an EAC member of SPEARHEAD).

10.4 times the computed counts, due to the $1/r^2$ scaling of the photon flux. Thus, we may expect large X-ray flares to be able to cause counting rates totaling some tens per minute in SIXS-P electron channels in orbit around Mercury. Note, however, that our estimate does not take into account pile-up resulting from photons with energies below the SIXS detection threshold. Since the flare X-ray spectra are very soft (e.g., Fig. 5), this could lead to higher counting rates in response to X-ray flares than estimated in this study.

Figure 12: Effective area for photon detection of SIXS-P for a parallel beam normal to the Side 0 detector, broken down to responses of the individual electron energy channels.

Table 1: Computed counting rates of SIXS due to eight solar X-ray flares as observed by RHESSI (cf. Fig 11).

Flare	E1 [cps]	E2 [cps]	E3 [cps]	E4 [cps]
20020819	4.595e-03	7.068e-04	8.235e-05	3.950e-06
20020820 A	2.900e-03	7.869e-05	8.759e-07	0.000e+00
20020820 B	2.829e-02	5.743e-03	8.258e-04	3.447e-05
20031231	7.297e-04	1.284e-04	2.374e-05	1.460e-06
20040331	6.994e-04	1.135e-04	1.724e-05	1.032e-06
20041030 A	1.384e-03	1.585e-04	9.205e-06	3.139e-07
20041030 B	8.076e-03	1.639e-03	2.473e-04	1.226e-05
20041101	1.844e-03	1.605e-04	8.248e-06	1.162e-07

3 Conclusions

Methodology

This deliverable focuses on the recalibration of the photon sensitivity of the [SOHO/EPHIN](#) and [BepiColombo/SIXS](#) instruments. The approach included:

- **EPHIN Simulation:** The [GEANT4](#) toolkit was used to simulate the [EPHIN](#) detector's response to solar X-ray and γ -ray events, with particular attention to the [SSD A](#) segment and its detection thresholds.
- **Comparison with [RHESSI](#) Data:** The simulated detector counts were compared with actual [RHESSI](#) observations for specific solar flare events (October 22, 2014, and July 7, 2002).
- **Threshold Studies:** The [SSD A](#) detection threshold was varied (3, 15, and 30 keV) to assess its impact on observed counts and to reconcile the discrepancies between measured and simulated count rates.
- **BepiColombo/SIXS Simulation:** The photon sensitivity of the particle detector of [SIXS](#) ([SIXS-P](#)) was also simulated using its effective area for a zero zenith angle, focusing on its future application when exposed to solar activity.

Main Results

- The [EPHIN SSD A](#) segment's measured count rates during solar X-ray flares were found to be roughly 75–200 times higher than the simulated rates when assuming a 30 keV threshold. This discrepancy was significantly reduced when the threshold was lowered to approximately 15 keV.
- The results imply that the actual effective threshold of [SSD A](#) is closer to 15 keV, suggesting influences from electronics noise and other effects.
- The count rate patterns across [SSD A](#) segments also revealed segment-specific differences, indicating that segment degradation and other hardware effects must be accounted for.
- The [BepiColombo/SIXS-P](#) sensitivity was simulated, but could not yet be validated with observational data, as the spacecraft had not been exposed to the Sun during its cruise configuration.

Bibliography

- Agostinelli, S., Allison, J., Amako, K., et al. 2003, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A, 506, 250
- Detrick, D. L. & Hill, S. M. 2007, Space Weather, 5
- Golub, L., Deluca, E., & et al. 2007, Solar Physics, 243, 63
- Huovelin, J., Vainio, R., Kilpua, E., et al. 2020, Space Science Reviews, 216
- Krucker, S., Hurford, G. J., Grimm, O., & et al. 2020, Astronomy & Astrophysics, 642, A15
- Kühl, P., Heber, B., Gómez-Herrero, R., et al. 2020, Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate, 10, 53
- Köberle, M., Heber, B., Kühl, P., et al. 2024, Deliverable 2.1: Report and delivery of the GEANT-4 models of SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN, Chandra/EPHIN, Solar Orbiter/ HET and BepiColombo/SIXS, Report, SPEARHEAD Project
- Köberle, M., Heber, B., Kühl, P., et al. 2025, Deliverable 2.3: Report and delivery of input and analysis programs to compute response functions using Geant4, Report, SPEARHEAD Project
- Lin, R. P. 2011, Space Sci. Rev., 159, 421
- Lin, R. P., Dennis, B. R., Hurford, G. J., & et al. 2002, Solar Physics, 210, 3
- Mason, J. P., Woods, T. N., Caspi, A., & et al. 2016, Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets, 53, 328
- Motorina, G. G., Lysenko, A. L., Anfinogentov, S. A., & Fleishman, G. D. 2020, Geomagnetism and Aeronomy, 60, 929
- Müller-Mellin, R., Kunow, H., Fleißner, V., et al. 1995, Sol. Phys., 162, 483
- NIST. 2025, X-Ray Mass Attenuation Coefficients, <https://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/XrayMassCoef>, accessed: 2025-05-05
- Sierks, H., Elent, I., Dröge, W., et al. 1997, in International Cosmic Ray Conference, Vol. 1, International Cosmic Ray Conference, 297
- Suarez-Garcia, E., Hajdas, W., Wigger, C., et al. 2006, Sol. Phys., 239, 149
- Thalmann, J. K., Su, Y., Temmer, M., & Veronig, A. M. 2015, ApJ, 801, L23